

INFLUENCE OF TiB₂ PARTICLES ON AGING BEHAVIOR OF IN-SITU TiB₂/AL-4.5Cu COMPOSITES

Rui Du¹, Qi Gao¹, Shusen Wu^{1*}, Shulin Lv¹, Zheng Wang¹

¹State Key Lab of Materials Processing and Die & Mould Technology, Huazhong University of
Science and Technology 1037 Luoyu Road, Wuhan 430074, China

¹ruidu@hust.edu.cn, ²460047522@qq.com, ³shulin317@hust.edu.cn, ⁵ zhengw@hust.edu.cn

*Corresponding author email: ssw636@hust.edu.cn

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ABSTRACT

In order to explicate the influence of TiB₂ particles on aging behavior of in-situ TiB₂/Al-4.5Cu composites, the evolvments of composites' microstructure and mechanical properties, and the mechanism of these evolutions have been systematically studied in this paper. Various testing techniques including SEM, TEM and XRD have been applied to investigate microstructure evolution in aging process, especially the precipitation of Al₂Cu phase. In addition, attention has also been paid to mechanical properties of the composites in aging process. Results indicate that TiB₂ particles have greatly enhanced the aging processes and the time to peak-aged condition in mechanical properties of the composites comes down from 20h to 8h.

1. Introduction

Particle reinforced aluminum matrix composites (PRAMCs) are under consideration as promising materials for various applications such as those in aerospace, military, transportation and so on due to the outstanding mechanical properties they possess [1~3]. Among numerous aluminum alloys, Al-Cu alloys are widely used in the aerospace industry because of their high strength and high hardness, but low deformation resistance of Al-Cu alloys has greatly inhibited their applications. TiB₂ ceramic is an excellent reinforcement in aluminum alloys among potential reinforcement particles like Al₂O₃, SiC, B₄C, TiC [4~6], since TiB₂ particles have high hardness, good thermodynamic stability, high corrosion resistance and low density. More importantly, there is no interface reaction between TiB₂ particles and alloy melt. In the meantime, in-situ techniques to fabricate TiB₂ particle reinforced metal matrix composites (MMCs) have been greatly improved since the second half of the last century [7~8]. Hence, in-situ TiB₂/Al-Cu MMCs can be easily synthesized without meeting difficulties such as poor wettability, formation of unwanted reaction products, etc., which are common to be seen in the development of ex-situ particulate MMCs [9~10].

Al-Cu alloys are always strengthened by heat treatment with the aid of aging sequence of θ (Al₂Cu) phase. The decomposition sequence of θ (Al₂Cu) phase is as follows [11]:

However, when involved to the heat treatment for particulate MMCs, technical designers often

draw on the experience of heat treatment of matrix alloys to decide the parameters, but ignore the presence of reinforcement particles. Actually, the addition of particles to the matrix drastically changes the system of composites, and this has been deemed to influence aging behavior greatly.

Quantitative and qualitative studies about the above influential factors have been made by several researchers. Bartels et al. [12] have analyzed the aging response of TiB₂/AA6061 alloy and his results has proved exist of TiB₂ particles enhanced the aging kinetics of matrix alloy. Salazar and Barrera [13] have also found similar enhancement in aging kinetics of AA7005 alloy with Al₂O₃ particles introduced to the matrix. Tianrong Hong et al. [14~15] have systemically discussed TiB₂ particles' influence on the heat treatment of in-situ TiB₂/AA2009 composites. His results revealed that the introduction of TiB₂ particles into the AA2009 matrix can not only increase the solution temperature ranges above the eutectic temperature of the basal alloy but also gives rise to two peak behaviors for the hardness of the composites as functions of aging time. Mandal et al. [16] believed TiB₂ particles accelerated the aging process in the Al-Cu alloy and he also found the rate of hardening on peak aging increased with increase in the amount of TiB₂ particles. From the above results, we can come to a preliminary conclusion that the introduction of TiB₂ particles are apparently response for a series of transformation. Nevertheless, these previous researches have observed some interesting phenomena, but they lack insights into the mechanism of these appearances. Meanwhile, foregoing relevant researches pay more attention on changes of hardness normally during aging process but seldom show solicitude for the mechanical properties, for instance, yield stress, ultimate tensile strength (UTS) and elongation, which impact directly on the effect of the heat treatment of the composites.

In this paper, authors want to investigate the influence of TiB₂ particles on the aging behavior of the in-situ TiB₂/Al-4.5Cu composites, and the evolvments of composites' microstructure and mechanical properties and the mechanism of these evolutions will also be discussed as the focus in this study.

2. Experimental procedures

The nominal chemical composition (in wt%) of the matrix alloy is Al-4.5%Cu. The in-situ 5vol% TiB₂/Al-4.5Cu composites were produced by the addition of preweighted mixture of K₂TiF₆ and KBF₄ salts into the alloy melt at 840°C through an exothermic reaction. Na₃AlF₆ was also added into reaction system as flux at 10% (in wt%) by the total mass of salts according to the experience. Salt-reaction process last generally for about one hour. After reaction, the slag was skimmed out as completely as possible, and the melt was cooled to 720°C and cast into a preheated permanent mould to get as-cast ingot.

Being a kind of high volume fraction TiB₂ particles reinforced composites, it's significant to consider the sediment and aggregation effects of the TiB₂ particulate. In accordance with Hashim's research [17], when the size of reinforced particles is below 10µm, gravitational sediment effect could be negligible. However, according to prophase research accomplished by Qi Gao et al. [18], the reinforcements fabricated by the way mentioned above are composed of submicron particles. So, only the agglomerations of TiB₂ particles should be taken into consideration. Qi Gao et al. [19] have also found that ultrasonic vibration treatment for 4 min throughout the molten bulk matrix can not only further refine α-Al grains but also eliminate agglomerations of TiB₂ particles in the liquid. Herein, in order to get a uniform distribution of TiB₂ particles with the liquidoid situation, the same ultrasonic vibration treatments for 4 min with vibration power is set at 2.8kW and the frequency of ultrasound is 20 kHz are applied in the TiB₂/Al-4.5Cu composites. Then the molten composites was immediately cast

into a preheated permanent mould mentioned above.

After casting, specimens were cut from the composites ingots. The aging behavior of the composites was studied by solution treated at 530 °C for 6 hours followed by quenching immediately in 70 °C water and aging at 180 °C for different intervals, i.e. 2h, 3h, 4h, 6h, 8h, 10h, 15h, 20h, 30h, 40h. During heat treatment, fluctuation of treated temperature was restricted within ± 2 °C. The phase compositions of composites were identified by X-ray diffraction (XRD) with Cu K α radiation operated at 40 kV and 40 mA. The composites were mechanically polished and then were etched with diluted hydrofluoric acid for 15s to reveal microstructure morphologies. Microstructure observation for the samples was implemented by scanning electron microscope (FEI Nova-450). A transmission electron microscope (FEI Tecnai-G2) was introduced for TEM observation and identification of precipitates in aging process. TEM thin foils were prepared by the combination use of mechanical technology and ion beam thinning. Finally, room temperature tensile tests for the samples were performed on SHIMADZU AG-100KN tester with a 1mm/min crosshead speed. The samples were machined according to ASTM specification B557M-84. To ensure the repetitive of composites, tensile data were taken from the average value of 5 specimens.

3. Results and discussions

3.1 Microstructure evolution in aging process

Fig. 1(a) shows the TiB₂ particles are wrapped by bright white Al₂Cu phase in as-cast state, the coarse Al₂Cu phase can be seen at high magnification from Fig. 1(b). When the temperature of the molten matrix drops below the liquidus temperature, solidification starts. Small crystals appear and grow continually as the temperature decrease. Due to the lattice disregistry between TiB₂ ceramics and aluminum grains is far over than 5%, it's quite difficult for TiB₂ particles to be engulfed by the moving liquid/solid interface of the matrix [20]. This is one of the criteria which cause the TiB₂ particles to be surrounded by the last freezing areas of the molten alloy during solidification process [21]. While the temperature falls below the solid temperature, Al₂Cu phases form along with the grain boundaries in the matrix and adhere to the TiB₂ particles. Backscattered electron (BSE) observation has been introduced to distinguish intermetallic Al₂Cu phase and TiB₂ particles co-existing at grain boundary regions.

Fig. 1. BSE microstructures of TiB₂/Al-4.5Cu composites in as-cast condition:
(a) Low magnification. (b) High magnification.

In the case of solutionised composites, the coarse Al₂Cu phase can hardly be seen in Fig. 2(a), only the clusters of TiB₂ particles gathering along grain boundaries could be observed in Fig. 2(b). These

results indicate that Al_2Cu phase almost dissolved into the matrix of composites and a nearly homogeneous solid solution of the matrix came into being.

Fig. 2. BSE microstructures of $\text{TiB}_2/\text{Al-4.5Cu}$ composites in as-solutionised condition:
(a) Low magnification. (b) High magnification.

After the solution heat treatment, the samples were then artificially aged at 180°C , and the decomposition of supersaturated solid solution began at this moment. As depicted in Fig. 3(a) and Fig. 3(b), few and tiny θ phase precipitates can be clearly seen in the composites. With time going by, there is an obvious increasing tendency for the volume fraction of the precipitates in the composites. The θ (Al_2Cu) phase is a body-centered tetragonal (bct) ($I4/mcm$, $a=0.607\text{ nm}$, $c=0.487\text{ nm}$). The selected area diffraction (SAD) patterns of the precipitations in Fig. 3(f) further confirmed that the identity of precipitates. It is apparent for us to find TiB_2 particles and high-density dislocations adjacent to them and dispersed Al_2Cu precipitates can also be found precipitate densely in the vicinity of TiB_2 particles.

Generally, it is accepted that due to the difference in the coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) between Al ($23.5 \times 10^{-6} \text{K}^{-1}$) and TiB_2 ($7 \times 10^{-6} \text{K}^{-1}$), the addition of TiB_2 particles into the composites would evidently promote the dislocation density in the matrix. These dislocations are deemed to act as nucleating sites during precipitation [22], thus this increase in dislocation density can result in precipitation enrichment of Al_2Cu phase.

Fig. 4 shows the TEM analysis results of TiB_2 particles. The typical hexagonal plate-like morphology of TiB_2 and dislocations adjacent to particles have been clearly observed. SAD patterns of the particles phase match hexagonal lattice of TiB_2 . These results have further confirmed exist of TiB_2 particles and its influence on the composites in accordance with that mentioned above.

Fig. 3. TEM micrographs of $\text{TiB}_2/\text{Al-4.5Cu}$ composites for different aging time:
(a) Aging for 2h; (b) Aging for 3h; (c) Aging for 4h; (d) Aging for 6h;
(e) Aging for 8h; (f) SAD patterns of Al_2Cu precipitates in (e).

Fig. 4. TEM results of TiB₂ particles.

Fig. 5 shows the morphology of composites while the aging time has surpassed 8h. It is shown that the amount of Al₂Cu precipitates added slowly and had little increase. However, comparing with micrographs in Fig. 3, the differences in the morphologies of θ phase has revealed that precipitates gradually grow larger and become coarse. Herein, this phenomenon has proved that the coarsening of Al₂Cu precipitates are dominant in this stage. When the aging time is extended to 20h or longer, Al₂Cu precipitates will greatly coarsen and appear nearly the same morphology and distribution as the as-cast condition, which are shown in Fig. 6.

According to the previous investigation on the precipitation of the classical Al-Cu alloys [23], no matter binary Al-Cu alloys or ternary Al-Cu-Mg alloys, unless the aging time lasts for 7h or longer, the precipitates of Al-Cu intermetallics can hardly be observed. However, fine Al₂Cu precipitates could be captured after aging for 2~3h in Fig. 3(a) and Fig. 3(b), and the amount of precipitates is quite considerable. Not only that, when the aging time is extended to 20h, the composites is almost on the condition of over aging. Nevertheless, as for matrix alloy, the amount of precipitates increases significantly when aging for 20h and this tendency will still continue for 3~5h according to previous studies [24]. Both of these two results firmly indicate that the aging kinetics of TiB₂/Al-4.5Cu composites has been greatly enhanced in this context.

Fig. 5. TEM micrographs of TiB₂/Al-4.5Cu composites for different aging time:
(a) Aging for 10h; (b) Aging for 15h; (c) Aging for 20h; (d) Aging for 30h;

Fig. 6. BSE microstructures of TiB₂/Al-4.5Cu composites for different aging time:
(a) Aging for 30h; (b) Aging for 40h;

Besides, there is a rare phenomenon which is still worth paying attention to. Generally, the θ phase precipitates in the Al-Cu alloys are distributed uniformly in other authors' researches [25]. However, TEM micrographs in Fig. 3 and Fig. 5 have revealed that the θ phase precipitates exhibit inhomogeneous

distribution with the effect of TiB_2 particles. T. Hong et al. [14-15] have established a model to describe this selective precipitation in the composites and divided the composites matrix into three zones according to their relative position with TiB_2 particles. They predicted that the precipitates are inclined to form in the zones with higher dislocation density which ought to be near the particles. Actually, this prediction matches well with not only their experimental results but also ours. It is also corresponded with the view that high dislocation density induced by TiB_2 particles will significantly accelerate the precipitation.

In addition, XRD analyses are also implemented to identify the phase composition of composites and the test results are shown in Fig. 7. Fig. 7(a) shows that the phase composition of composites remains unchanged after heat treatment and TiB_2 phase and Al_2Cu phase are also clear to identify. This results have further confirmed that the heat treatment, no matter solution treatment or aging treatment, has no effects on the phase composition of the composites. However, if we carefully investigate the main peaks of α -Al crystal in Fig. 7(a), a gradual shift in the Al peaks is evident to note. In Fig. 7(b), firstly, the main peak of α -Al in as-solutionised condition moved about 0.6° towards left comparing with the main peak in as-cast condition, which indicated an increase in the lattice parameters of α -Al. This results may be attributed to the dissolution of Al_2Cu into Al grains, which has noted in Fig. 2. When the aging treatment started, Cu atoms gradually precipitated from solid solution in the form of fine and dispersed Al_2Cu phase, which has shown in Fig. 3 and Fig. 5. The precipitation is accompanied by a decrease in the lattice parameters of Al which leads to the main peaks gradually return back to the condition of curve 1.

Fig. 7. XRD patterns of $\text{TiB}_2/\text{Al-4.5Cu}$ composites: (a) Patterns from 20° to 90° ; (b) Patterns from 37° to 39° . (1): in as-cast condition; (2): in as-solutionised condition; (3): aging for 4h; (4): aging for 10h; (5): aging for 20h;

3.2 Mechanical properties of the composites in aging process

Firstly, in Fig. 8, it is clear to see that yield strength (YS) and ultimate tensile strength (UTS) of the composites have reached to the maximum value when aging for 8h. Thus, aging for 8h is the peak-aged condition of the composites in this context. Meanwhile, peak-aged condition also acts as a turning point in the aging behavior. If the aging time is less than 8h, YS and UTS of the composites keep rising with time going by. However, if the aging time has surpassed 8h, YS and UTS gradually decrease and return to nearly the same level with as-cast condition. It should be pointed out that according to the former research [19], the YS and UTS of composites in as-cast condition are 137 and 263, respectively.

Generally, it is believed that the strengthening contribution from TiB_2 particles does not changed significantly during aging process. As a result, the changes on mechanical properties of the composites

can only be attributed to the presence of Al_2Cu phase. After the solution heat treatment, Al_2Cu phase almost dissolved into the matrix, which has been proved in Fig. 2 and Fig. 7, and the solid solution strengthening is the dominant mechanism at this time. Thus, the YS and UTS of composites in as-solutionised condition has improved 9% and 10% compared with composites in as-cast condition. When the aging process began, fine Al_2Cu precipitates with needle shape formed near the TiB_2 particles, which has been observed in Fig 3. Due to Cu atoms gradually precipitated from matrix alloy, the effect of solid solution strengthening had been weakened. However, because of hard and brittle property of the Al_2Cu precipitates, they acted as a strong obstacle to slip of dislocations in the matrix, thus provided excellent precipitation strengthening of the composites. In addition, when the Al_2Cu precipitated, a new phase formed. As a result, grain boundaries between two phases were created. Boundaries interfered the slip of dislocations thereby strengthening the metal. Not only that, there is also CTE mismatch existing between Al and Al_2Cu . As stated earlier, CTE mismatches would generate dislocations thus further strengthen the composites. In a word, precipitation strengthening, boundary strengthening together with CTE mismatch strengthening have greatly enhanced the mechanical properties of the composites. For example, in comparison to as-cast condition, YS and UTS in peak-aged condition have improved 34% and 37%, respectively.

When the aging time has surpassed 8h, the decreasing of tensile properties indicates that there are deleterious mechanisms acting to reduce the mechanical properties. Since the Al_2Cu precipitates have a tendency to fracture but not to deform under tensile stress because they possess high hardness and low ductility, the larger Al_2Cu precipitates, the lower fracture stress because they usually act as the source of severe cracks. In fact, the coarsening procedure of Al_2Cu precipitates has been easily observed in Fig. 5 and Fig. 6, hence the coarse Al_2Cu precipitates should be blame for the decreasing in mechanical properties.

A comparison on the aging response between $\text{TiB}_2/\text{Al-4.5Cu}$ composites and Al-4.5Cu matrix alloy has also be made in this context. Fig. 8 shows the mechanical properties of the composites and matrix alloy as a function of aging time. In the absence of TiB_2 particles, the curves of Al-4.5Cu matrix alloy increase gently in both Fig. 8(a) and Fig. 8(b) and the peak-aged condition of matrix alloy occupies 20h to reach. However, the time required to reach peak-aged condition decrease from 20h to 8h (60% decrease) in the presence of TiB_2 particles. Thus, we can come to a conclusion that the presence of TiB_2 particles can greatly enhance the aging kinetics of Al-4.5Cu alloy. This is in agreement with the results in Fig. 3 and Fig. 5, and the mechanism of this phenomenon has been demonstrated in Fig. 4.

Fig. 8. Mechanical properties of the composites and matrix alloy as a function of aging time:
(a): Yield Strength; (b): Ultimate Tensile Strength (UTS).

4. Conclusions

In this study, the aging behavior of in-situ TiB₂/Al-4.5Cu composites has been systematically studied and the main conclusions can be summarized as follows:

1. The introduction of TiB₂ particles will induce high-density dislocations adjacent to TiB₂ particles. These dislocations are regarded as the nucleating sites of Al₂Cu precipitates during precipitation thus aging kinetics of TiB₂/Al-4.5Cu composites has been greatly enhanced.
2. The precipitation of Al₂Cu phase not only has been significantly accelerated by the presence of TiB₂ particles but also exhibits inhomogeneous distribution that Al₂Cu precipitates mainly locate on the vicinity of TiB₂ particles. Besides, the precipitation procedure of Al₂Cu phase can be distinctly divided into two stages. In the first stage, there is an obvious increasing tendency for the volume fraction of the precipitates in the composites. When the aging time has surpassed 8h, the coarsening of Al₂Cu precipitates are dominant.
3. The evolution on mechanical properties of the composites can be divided into two stages as well. While the aging time is less than 8h, the fine and dispersed Al₂Cu precipitates can strengthen the composites and mechanical properties reach to the maximum value in 8h. When the aging time has surpassed 8h, coarse Al₂Cu precipitates will cause mechanical properties deteriorating. Compared with the aging behavior of Al-4.5Cu matrix alloy, the time to peak-aged condition in mechanical properties of the composites comes down from 20h to 8h with the effect of TiB₂ particles.

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